

Active Anthraquinoids from *Rheum webbianum* Royle

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In consideration of our interest on *Rheum webbianum* (Polygonaceae) Royle for its commercial use, we examined the roots of the plant and report herein the isolation of 1,8-dihydroxy-3-methyl-, 1,6,8-trihydroxy-3-methyl- and 1,8-dihydroxy-3-hydroxy-methyl-anthraquinone.

The roots (700 g) of the plant (collected from Pindari glaciers, 4000 m, in U.P. Kumaon Himalaya) were shade dried, pulverised and soxhlet-extracted with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated under vacuum and the concentrate was partitioned with CHCl_3 - H_2O (1:1, v/v). Both the layers were separated and the chloroform-solubles were concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel G column. On successive elution of the column with n-hexane, n-hexane-benzene and benzene with different proportions, three anthraquinoid-positive fractions (A), (B) and (C) were collected in amorphous forms.

Homogeneity of each fraction was determined by tlc and hplc (Water Associate instrument) using variable wavelength (190-750 nm) uv detector.

- (A); $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_4 = \text{OH}$
 (B); $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_3 = \text{OH}$, $\text{R}_4 = \text{OH}$
 (C); $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}_4 = \text{OH}, \text{OH}$

On eluting the silica gel G column with n-hexane-benzene (9:1) and on crystallisation of the resulting solid yielded a brilliant yellow coloured compound-A (900 mg), m.p. 192° (M^+ 254) which responded to the usual colour reaction for anthraquinonoid⁴; the diacetate, m.p. 127°; λ_{max} (MeOH) 228, 257, 277, 287 and 429 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 470, 3 080, 1 680 (conjug. C=O) and 1 630 cm^{-1} (chelated C=O) and ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectral data identified the compound as 1,8-dihydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone. Its identity was further ascertained by co-ir and co-hplc with an authentic sample.

Further, on eluting the column with the same solvent n-hexane-benzene (9:2), compound B (100 mg), m.p. 250°, was isolated. It formed a trimethyl derivative⁴, m.p. 205°, and gave characteristic colour reactions^{3,4} of anthraquinoids^{3,4}. It was identified as 1,6,8-trihydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone by means of spectral data, ms (270, 100%), λ_{max} (MeOH) 222, 226, 252, 289 and 436 nm; ν_{max} 3 390, 1 675 and 1 630 cm^{-1} , m/z 270 (100%) as well

as ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectral data and comparing it with the authentic sample.

The third yellow compound C (80 mg), m.p. 220°, was isolated with the same eluting solvent system n-hexane-benzene (7:3). Based on its colour reactions^{3,4} and spectral data, ms (M^+ 270, 100%), λ_{max} (MeOH) 225, 254, 276, 287 and 257 sh cm^{-1} ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300, 3 050, 1 650 and 1 610 cm^{-1} , ^1H and ^{13}C nmr as well as by comparing the results with an authentic sample, it was identified as 1,8-dihydroxy-3-hydroxymethyl-anthraquinone.

The spasmolytic activity of the anthraquinoid 1,8-dihydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone is well established⁴. Its presence as a major constituent in the herb seems to be responsible for the spasmolytic properties.

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Amino Acids of *Fleurya interrupta*

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FLEURYA interrupta Gaudich^{1,2} (Syn. *F. glomerata* Gaud.) ; (Hindi and Bengali : Lal bichua) belonging to the family *Urticaceae* is the only species recorded in India to be found in Tripura, Khasi hills, Bengal, Bihar, Orissa and South India. The leaves of this plant are reported to be applied locally for carbuncle in Phillipines ; a decoction of the roots is used as a diuretic. We investigated chemically for the first time the aerial parts of this plant. We report herein the isolation, identification and relative occurrence of eleven amino acids, out of which five are essential.

The aerial parts of the young plant (about 3 months old) were collected from the tilla area of Agartala in June 1985. The air-dried milled aerial parts (150 g) were extracted with petrol (b.p. 60-80°; 2 dm³) and rectified spirit (2 dm³) successively by percolation. The alcoholic extract